

Streamlined Sharing of Computational Narratives

Science is a global enterprise that builds and organizes human understanding of the universe with testable explanations and predictions. The goal of science – to improve human understanding of the universe – is achieved through the *exchange of information*. Science advances when humans collaborate to discover and learn from each other. We propose to improve information sharing within, between, and beyond communities using open source science infrastructure and NASA data.

Opportunity

NASA has committed to shaping science in the cloud streaming era to make it more open. NASA's commitments to open science are expressed in [policy \(SPD41a\)](#), programs ([TOPS](#), [OSSI](#)) investments ([NASA-AWS Space Act Agreement](#), [funding opportunities](#)), and transition planning ([Data and Compute Architecture Study](#)).

Innovative **NASA communities**¹ have begun to use *common workflows* across diverse research areas² using NASA data. These communities operate like "**digital villages**" formed next to a "data lake". Three challenges have been identified by interactions with these communities:

1. Systems for exchanging scientific content (text, code, data) within and between communities need to be improved,
2. Data from NASA missions need to become more discoverable and interoperable,
3. Achieving open science goals requires a robust implementation of social and technological innovations.

¹ These communities include [CIROH](#), [CryoCloud](#), [earthaccess](#), [EarthScope](#), [HelioCloud](#), [IEEE-GRSS](#), [EarthScope](#), [icepyx](#), [LEAP](#), [LinkedEarth](#), [NSIDC](#), [PyHC](#), [OpenSARlab](#), [Openscapes](#), [Pangeo](#), [NASA SARP](#), [SlideRule](#), [U.S. Greenhouse Gas Center](#) and [VEDA](#). These communities vary in the ways they connect to NASA. Some were built by and for NASA employees. Some were convened with grants awarded by NASA. Some are organized around research lines using NASA data but are otherwise disconnected from the agency.

² Workflows built on open source science infrastructure are transforming research in atmosphere, biosphere, climate, cryosphere, exoplanets, geophysics, heliophysics, human-environment interactions, hydrology, land processes, oceanography, paleoclimatology, weather and beyond.

Improving the *common workflows* -- social processes for learning and discovery using open source science infrastructure -- with a main focus on the first challenge is the target of the planned work. This proposal will build and experiment with "village libraries" using available open source components to improve science information sharing.

Problem

The way we improve humanity's understanding of the universe -- **the way we science** -- is through the **exchange of information**. Science advances through a global dialogue³ using a variety of information container formats⁴ and channels.

Traditional information sharing in science is inefficient. Discoveries are made using one format (data ingestion and exploration with code in a terminal on a laptop in a cafe), reported to collaborators in a second format (email with subject line: Eureka!), announced semi-privately in a third format (Powerpoint presentation in a university seminar), and shared more widely in a fourth format (PDF file). Interested readers often struggle to reproduce the result using the reported recipes in the article. Discovery information moves slowly and incompletely through these various formats like fluid diffuses through porous media.

The open source science ecosystem has improved methods for producing, collaborating and sharing science. These improvements include new information container formats, like [MyST markdown](#), that can be used for reading, exploring, collaborating, sharing, publishing -- the **same format is universally used throughout all phases of the science project lifecycle**. These formats provide reader-friendly and author-friendly ways to interact with text, mathematical notation, code in various programming languages, figures, citations, and data. Information in these formats are called **computational narratives**, an abstraction of traditional paper-like formats. Computational narratives can be printed to paper, rendered statically in paper-like formats such as PDF, and rendered interactively in JupyterLab, Jupyter Book, R Studio,

³ Example dialogues include: sender(s)<>receiver(s), author<>reader, presenter<>audience, instructor<>student, collaborator<>collaborator, instrument<>scientist, ai<>human.

⁴ Scientific information container formats include: conversation, handwritten letters, library book, seminar presentation, chalkboard, email message, Microsoft Word file, PDF preprint, research article, blog post, code repository, ...

Visual Studio Code, etc. When the right resources are available, simply clicking a hyperlink can launch a computational narrative fully rendered with interactivity.

The proposed work addresses the problem that "digital villages" adjacent to NASA data are *inconsistently benefitting* from their use of new information container formats and channels for exchanging⁵ scientific content. The proposed work will systematically implement and iteratively improve sharing systems across a collection of NASA communities.

Solution

Our vision is for an open science ecosystem where discovery information moves rapidly and completely within and between science communities like turbulent transport. We will lower the friction to reproducibly share scientific information.

The proposed work will help NASA communities launch and maintain "community libraries" to improve sharing of scientific content, especially content involving code and interactivity enabled by adjacent computation and data. Our work will systematize an inspiring patchwork implementation of open source sharing methods used inconsistently across the "digital villages". The proposed approach is designed to integrate with and leverage the interactive computing platforms deployed near NASA data that these communities are heavily using today.

The planned work will deliver a coherent implementation of an **open source system for sharing** built with open source components:

1. Build a **community library scaffold**. A traditional library is a building that contains books. Similarly, the community library scaffold will enable the community to store, showcase and share the computational narratives they have produced. The scaffold will be a website template built as a static content management system using [MyST markdown](#) resembling the [JupyterBook Gallery](#).

⁵ Open source tools, frameworks and libraries for sharing interactive content include git, nbgitpuller, JupyterHub, BinderHub, JupyterLab, Jupyter Book, MyST, R Studio, Quarto and more. The proposed work will implement a coherent sharing system for NASA communities using these components. The system will be iteratively improved with feedback from the communities as they develop and share interactive content.

2. Develop a **tutorial** and documentation on **how to implement the community library scaffold and use MyST markdown** to effectively create and share content for a NASA community. Organize hackathon events with communities to work through the tutorial, deploy the library scaffold, and start adding content to their community's library. Experiment with different methods to deploy (GitHub pages, Vercel, Netlify, adjacent to the community's JupyterHub, ...) the community's library. Use feedback from the events to iteratively improve the tutorial and "how to" documentation.
3. Publish a **volume of interactive proceedings** from a community's workshop using the library scaffold in collaboration with a publisher. The American Geophysical Union is [experimenting with interactive publishing](#).
4. Implement [Jupyter AI](#) in the community JupyterHubs to allow for exploratory work with **AI research assistants trained on the content in the community library**.
5. Implement easy-to-use **publish to community library** and **generate "magic link" ([nbgitpuller](#)) to share interactive content** workflows in JupyterLab.
6. [Enable launches](#) of library content into interactive computing sessions by connecting the library to the community's JupyterHub, a Binder service or [JupyterLite](#). Launchers transport the reader to a new browser tab where the library content is rendered with interactivity.
7. [Enable interactivity](#) of content rendered in the library using [Thebe](#).
8. Develop **application programming interfaces (APIs) that link a community's content stored elsewhere to the community library**. The community's library should connect to the community's [Zotero group](#), [Zenodo space](#) or other community-selected collections of preprints and articles.
9. Explore enrichments to the community's AI research assistants by training on content from Zotero, Zenodo or other collections.
10. Enable communities to document and institutionalize open science best practices by pre-populating community libraries with templates (code of conduct, open science and data management plans, inclusion plans, contribution guidelines).

The open source system for sharing will be developed iteratively through a **series of social interactions using the system** to produce and share interactive content. The series of virtual and in-person events – workshops,

hackathons, tutorials, documentation jams, conferences organized with NASA communities that have expressed interest in collaborating on this project – will generate shared content and insights on how the system can be improved. The events in the first year will be designed to provide rapid feedback on the sharing system’s technical design and implementation. The second year events will validate the first year’s technical innovations and be designed as experiments to socially innovate. The aim for the events in the final three years will be to produce interactive content, iteratively improve the sharing system, and establish robust open science practices for sharing computational narratives in NASA communities.

Sustainability

The technological advances made through this project will be shared as open source⁶ software and designed around standards. The systems we build will be replicable and work interoperably across the leading data center platforms to avoid commercial cloud vendor lock-in. This approach to building systems for sharing interactive content – open source software designed to be replicable across the cloud vendors – ensures the sustainability of the technology systems used for science. Our approach aims to advance toward a vital imperative: the systems used by humanity to understand the universe should be a public good.

Interactive content generated by the communities through this project will be shared under [open licenses](#) specified by the communities (e.g., CC BY-4.0, MIT).

Robust changes to the way communities share scientific content requires social innovation. A metaphor that guides our proposed work – experiments with “village libraries” for improved content sharing within and between “digital villages” working adjacent to a “data lake” – is partly inspired by the Carnegie libraries built across thousands of towns a century ago. Investments for new libraries in towns were made based on the [Carnegie Formula](#): eligible towns had to demonstrate commitment to their library. The NASA communities that

⁶ Software developed by the proponent under this project will be released under the [BSD 3-Clause License](#).

collaborate on this project will make similar demonstrations⁷ of commitment to the long-term sustainability of the content they generate and share.

With funding from NASA, the proposed work will contribute to an open science ecosystem where computational narratives – scientific information rich with text, code, visualizations, and data – are shared rapidly within and between science communities.

Specifics

The proposed work will streamline and improve content sharing among NASA communities that are using cloud-hosted interactive computing platforms such as JupyterHub and RStudio. SMD science communities [ASF](#), [OpenSARlab](#), [HelioCloud](#), and [NSIDC](#) share content on GitHub. [CryoCloud](#) shares content using [Jupyter Book](#). [VEDA](#) documentation and the [NASA EarthData Cloud Cookbook](#) are built with [Quarto](#). In all of these cases, a NASA community is sharing interactive content rendered statically, with some offering under-resourced and slow-to-launch interactive sessions via [MyBinder](#). Readers who wish to dive in and interact with the content more deeply encounter obstacles. These ways of sharing evolved over time. Statically rendered notebooks on GitHub were improved with Jupyter Book (based on [Sphinx](#)) and Quarto. The proposed work will assist these and other NASA communities with implementing the next generation sharing system based on [MyST](#). Letters of support⁸ for this proposal from a diverse collection of NASA stakeholders indicates widespread interest in the proposed approach to improve interactive content sharing.

MyST, a recent project developed by the [Executable Books Project](#), compliments and extends Jupyter Book. MyST is a robust ecosystem for working with interactive computational and scientific content that includes a [specification of a data structure for documents](#), a [markup language](#) that is a superset of CommonMark markdown and TeX, and a [parsing system](#) that

⁷ Communities will be required to conform to open science best practices. Communities will be encouraged to make in-kind and financial investments to support the events organized through this project. Communities will be asked to confirm their intentions to maintain and improve the libraries they create.

⁸ Supporting letters for this proposal from NASA communities and adjacent stakeholders (CryoCloud, Colorado School of Mines [ice penetrating radar], Curvenote, Development Seed, NASA Student Airborne Research Program [SARP], NASA Goddard Space Flight Center [SlideRule], National Snow and Ice Data Center [earthaccess], Openscapes, University of New Hampshire [icepyx], University of Colorado [PyHC]) are included in the appendix.

allows for [exporting](#) documents written in MyST to many standard formats ([PDF](#), [Word](#), [JATS](#), [html](#), [LaTeX](#)). Notebooks in [.ipynb format can be converted back-and-forth](#) to MyST format. MyST enables novel [reuse](#) of scientific content. Documents written in MyST can be made interactive using [Thebe](#) or [launched](#) into JupyterHub, BinderHub, or JupyterLite sessions.

MyST is transformational and ready for widespread use. Our project will assist NASA communities with iterative improvements around sharing of interactive content through wider adoption of MyST.

MyST and the closely associated Jupyter Book projects are currently governed under the Executable Books Project. The community has [proposed to move](#) these projects under Project Jupyter. [Software developed under the Executable Books Project is shared](#) as open source under BSD 3-Clause or MIT licenses. Establishing Jupyter Book and MyST under Project Jupyter contributes to improved conditions for the long-term sustainability of the open source software. Software in this project is developed in the open with code shared in public repositories on GitHub following an open development model with this [contribution guide](#) and in alignment with the Executable Books Project [code of conduct](#). The code describes expected behavior that contributes toward a positive environment and specifies unacceptable behavior. The code includes an escalating system of interventions and mechanisms of enforcement designed to protect community members and ensure compliance.

Contributions into the open sharing system will be encouraged and managed through the open source governance process established by the Executable Books Project. People working together on the MyST ecosystem used to develop the community library scaffolding will operate following the code of conduct established by the Executable Books Project.

The communities served through this project may have their own community defined best practices. Communities that organize events under this project will be required to conform to the [NASA TOPS Code of Conduct](#) or to a similarly robust code of conduct specified by the community. Content generated by communities through this project will be required to openly share their contributions under open licenses (CC-BY-4.0, MIT, or similar). We will strongly encourage organizers of community events under this project to complete the [Open Science 101 training developed and shared by NASA](#)

[TOPS](#). We will encourage communities that develop content through this project to implement their own community codes of conduct, contribution guidelines, [inclusion plans](#), and [open science and data management plans \(OSDMP\)](#) inside their community library. We will assist communities in documenting and implementing these open science best practices by offering templates for these community policy documents.

Shared interactive content from NASA communities will widen access to NASA science information and mission data. Templates for community codes of conduct, open science and data management plans, and inclusion plans will assist NASA communities to transform open science behaviors into robust habits.

Our project will develop an improved gallery for showcasing interactive content sites based on the [Jupyter Book gallery](#) using MyST. This gallery will serve as a content scaffolding system that NASA communities can use to share documentation sites, tutorials, articles and other interactive content. Our project will heavily use and iteratively improve existing documentation available on the various Jupyter Book and MyST sites. Feedback, through surveys and synchronous discussions during the events, from NASA communities on these sites will be used to improve documentation and the overall interactive content sharing ecosystem. This feedback will be captured into publicly visible issues on GitHub in repositories associated with the upstream software projects. Content developed by NASA communities will be deployed on sites managed by those communities adjacent to and leveraging the communities' interactive computing platforms. The systems we will support can be deployed using several content delivery infrastructures. Successful implementation will be measured by the amount and quality of the content shared, the readership of that content, and satisfaction reports from the communities we serve. We anticipate that the project will generate one or more special interactive proceedings volumes from workshops organized by the communities the project supports.

Our project will collaborate with [Curvenote](#), a company working to support the MyST ecosystem, and the [MyST Steering Council](#).

We plan to assign annual personnel resources on average of 1.5 FTE for technical support and content support of MyST and the community library scaffolding (salary \$75K/y), 0.35 FTE for infrastructure and development

engineering (salary \$150K/y), 0.25 FTE for community success (best practices guidance on events, training on use of MyST, the sharing system, adoption and implementation of open science policies and behaviors) (\$120K/y), 0.1 FTE for leadership (\$150K/y) and 0.33 FTE for admin support (\$100K/y). We envision this project will operate approximately five community-organized events focused on content generation per year. We expect communities to contribute in-kind and financially to these events. We plan to invest \$15K/event to cover travel and support costs on average. This works out to approximately \$275K/y before indirect costs.

The open sharing system will initially be launched for use by a small number of communities. After an iteration or two, we will make the sharing system generally available for deployment by all NASA communities working with NASA data adjacent to an interactive computing platform. Documentation on how to use the sharing system will be shared publicly.

Open Science and Data Management Plan (OSDMP)

The software developed as part of this project will be shared as open source through the aligned upstream projects (MyST, Jupyter Book, Executable Books Project). The software will be shared under open licenses (BSD 3-Clause, MIT).

This project will support NASA communities with their implementation of open science and data management plans. Communities that wish to participate in events organized under this project will be required to specify their OSDMP, code of conduct and inclusion plans. The project will enable NASA communities to implement open science best practices by pre-populating the community library scaffolds we develop with templates for these policy documents and social innovations to implement community behavior in alignment with open science, data management, inclusion, and conduct best practices.

Inclusion Plan

A majority of members on this project's team have completed Open Science 101. Our team has experience building inclusivity into prior projects. A first action for our team at the launch of this project is to assemble for our Team Expectations meeting. This meeting will implement the roles and responsibilities we've sketched out while building this proposal and implement the necessary policies for our project's success. Our team will combine our experiences building inclusive teams and [best practices guidance from NASA](#) to define an Inclusion Plan for our team, the sub-teams we build to implement the project, and a template inclusion plans for the NASA communities we will support through the events we have planned.

Work plan

Draft work plans for the first year and the first three years of the project are rendered as GANTT charts below.

Streamlined Sharing of Computational Narratives (2025-2027)

